

Effect of fungicides on neck BI incidence and yield of Pakistani Basmati.

Treatment	Rate of application/ha (on formulation basis)	Disease incidence (%)	Disease control over check (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Increase in yield over check (%)
Pyroquilon	30 kg DI + 40 kg PI ^a	12.7	69.8	3.2	16.3
Chlobenthiazole	30 kg DI + 40 kg PI	6.0	85.7	3.1	13.9
IBP	30 kg DI + 40 kg PI	29.3	30.2	2.9	4.0
Edifenphos	5 liters in 60 kg sand DI + 5 liters in 60 kg sand PI	18.0	57.1	3.0	7.1
Check	-	42.0	-	2.8	-
LSD 0.05		4.7			

^aDI = at disease initiation. PI = at panicle initiation.

Rice yellow dwarf (RYD) disease in Assam, India

K. B. Pun and G. R. Das, Regional Agricultural Research Station (RARS), Assam Agricultural University, Karimganj 788710. Assam, India

RYD symptoms have been noticed in rainfed lowland, transplanted autumn rice (Mar/Apr to Aug) in the Barak Valley Zone of Assam since 1989. Plants showed pronounced stunting, profuse tillering, uniform, pale yellow leaves, and lack of panicle development. Panicles were short with chaffy grains if they emerged. Similar symptoms were observed in ratoon crops.

We observed 7.50 indigenous entries from the autumn rice germplasm collection of RARS during 1991. Of these, 179 showed RYD symptoms, with 3-12% of the plants infected. Recommended varieties—DR92, Cauvery, Rasi, Culture 1, and Akashi—exhibited similar symptoms.

RYD had never been reported before in this zone and therefore had to be confirmed. We conducted transmission studies using green leafhopper (GLH) during 1991 kharif. We gave 2d- and 3d-instar GLH nymphs acquisition access feeding for 24 h on apparently RYD-infected Cauvery plants. After 30 d of incubation, the viruliferous insects were allowed inoculation access feeding for 24 h on 11-d-old seedlings for each variety. Visible symptoms of RYD appeared in all the test varieties 22-27 d after inoculation.

Spraying RYD-infected plants with a 250-ppm solution of oxytetracycline twice at a 15-d interval caused a remission of the symptoms. These results confirmed the occurrence of RYD in Assam. □

Integrated pest management—insects

Fall-off rates of *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) and efficiency of the predator *Limnognus fossarum* (F.)

M. L. P. Almazan and K. L. Heong, IRRI

The water strider *Limnognus fossarum* (F.) (Hemiptera: Gerridae) is common in wetland ricefields. It often feeds on brown planthoppers (BPH) that fall off the rice plants. We determined fall-off rates of the BPH and efficiency of *L. fossarum* in attacking those BPH that fell off.

BPH-resistant IR64 and susceptible TN 1 grown in the laboratory were used. The experimental arena consisted of a potted rice plant (35 d old) trimmed to five tillers and placed in a plastic container filled with water and enclosed in a cylindrical mylar cage (17 cm diameter, 50 cm high). The water level was kept at 1 cm above the brim of the pot.

In the fall-off study, 1-d-old BPH females were introduced into the experimental arena at densities of 5, 10, 20, 30, and 60, each replicated five times. BPH in the water were recorded 24 h later.

The predation rate of *L. fossarum* was measured in a different experiment replicated five times using the same BPH densities. We released a 1-d-old female *L. fossarum* inside the experimental arena containing 1-d-old BPH females. We recorded the BPH consumed after 24 h.

The number of BPH that fell off the plants was related to density (see figure). Fall-off was highest at density 60, and was significantly higher in IR64 than in

All of the fungicides significantly reduced neck BI incidence. Chlobenthiazole proved most effective and reduced incidence by 85.7%, increasing yield by 13.9%. Soil application of edifenphos was the least effective (see table). □

Rate of fall-off of BPH and consumption by *L. fossarum* at different BPH densities.

TN1. The rate of BPH consumption by *L. fossarum* increased with density. The number of BPH attacked was significantly higher in IR64 than in TN1 at the higher densities.

Number of BPH consumed and fall-off were not correlated, however. The number consumed, especially at lower BPH densities, was generally higher than the number of those falling off. This indicates that the water strider did not only prey on BPH that fell into the water, but that it also attacked BPH on the plant. Consumption was higher with the resistant cultivar IR64, suggesting that the fall-off also increased BPH consumption by *L. fossarum*. □